

INTERFACIAL CRACK ARREST IN SANDWICH BEAMS SUBJECTED TO FATIGUE LOADING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

A novel crack arresting device is implemented in sandwich beams tested using the Sandwich Tear Test (STT) method. In the research presented in this paper, fatigue loading was applied to the specimens to propagate the crack and determine the effect of the crack stopper. Digital image correlation was used through the duration of the fatigue experiment to track the strain evolution as the crack tip advances. Strains were related to crack tip propagation and post arrest re-initiation of the crack. Furthermore, a finite element model was used to calculate the energy release rate, mode mixity and simulate crack propagation and arrest of the crack under fatigue loading conditions. The experimental study has demonstrated that the crack stopper device is capable of deflecting and arresting propagating face/core interface cracks under fatigue conditions, and the ability to predict this behavior using numerical tools has been demonstrated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich construction has been much celebrated for its excellent structural properties that pioneer the light weight construction design [1]. Sandwich structures owe their exceptional structural performance to the I-Beam concept that is applied using two thin layers of a stiff and strong material (facesheets) separated and bonded together by a weaker and more compliant material (core). In a structural form, the facesheets are responsible for carrying the in-plane stresses while the core carries the out of plane shear stresses. Loss of the structural integrity in sandwich components results in a different load distribution which as a consequence might present a completely unexpected structural behavior. Premature failure, facesheet buckling, wrinkling are phenomena that may occur when the bond between the face-sheets and the core fails. This leads to a separation of the face-sheet and core materials, referred to as debonding. Debonds may be caused in sandwich structures due to local load introduction, impact loads, processing and manufacturing. Since totally avoiding debonds in sandwich components is impossible, especially as structures become larger, the use of new design methods to account for such debonds must be implemented in the structural design process of sandwich structures. Rising interest in interfacial debond behavior of sandwich components has led to several analytical, experimental and numerical studies. One approach is to consider debonds in the framework of fracture mechanics, as interfacial cracks fracture mechanics measures are commonly used to describe the conditions of debond expansion or arrest. Several studies have set the theoretical background [2-7], but it is only in the most recent studies that numerical tools have been utilized successfully to simulate interface crack growth. Several methods have been proposed based on the Finite Element analysis

framework that have been successfully used to simulate interface crack propagation. The Virtual Crack Closing Technique (VCCT) [8], the Crack Surface Displacement Extrapolation method (CSDE) [9-10] as well as cohesive zone modelling (CZM) [11] are some of the most used tools. The cycle jump technique has been proposed and utilized to reduce the calculated loading cycles of fatigue simulations. In this study the CSDE method together with the cycle jump technique is used to simulate interface crack propagation in sandwich beams under fatigue loading conditions. Crack deflection and propagation in the core structure is simulated as well as crack arrest.

It will be shown that numerical simulations can be used to assess and predict the behavior of crack arresters. In the past numerical tools have been used to assess the behavior of previously proposed crack arresting devices. Hirose [12-13] in his many studies proposing crack arresting concepts used the FE analysis method to demonstrate the effectiveness of the crack stopping elements. In all cases the energy release rate and the mode mixity angle of the crack are of high importance as they reflect the nature and tendency of the crack to propagate. In these previous studies an attempt to model the whole fatigue experiment with crack propagation, arrest and post arrest propagation was not attempted. This will be attempted in this study by using FE analysis, experimental observations from fatigue testing on beams including crack stoppers and fatigue data (S-N curve) of core materials. Finally Jakobsen et al. [14-16] tested a new type of crack arrester, the peel stopper that used a more compliant material to re-direct the interface crack away from the actual interface trapping it at the center of the arrester. Jakobsen performed static tests with beams showcasing the ability of the peel stopper to deflect a crack from the interface and arrest it. Since all the tests were under quasi-static loading conditions no indication on the performance of the peel stopper under fatigue loading conditions was gained.

In the present study an improved version of Jakobsens peel stopper concept is tested under fatigue loading conditions. The STT set-up is chosen for its more representative and less generic nature as a sandwich beam test set-up. The new peel stopper will be evaluated for its ability to arrest a crack and its potential to enhance damage tolerance of larger sandwich components under fatigue loading conditions.

2. EXPERIMENT

The new peel stopper concept, Figure 1, has been implemented in beam specimens that have been tested under fatigue loading conditions using the Sandwich Tear Test (STT) set-up, Figure 2. The peel stopper was found capable of increasing the fatigue life expectancy of a sandwich beam for up to more than 60% [17]. Four specimens were tested in total. The peel stopper is evaluated based on the number of cycles under which the crack stays at the arrest point before re-initiation occurs. The cycles are compared with the overall fatigue life of the specimen. DIC cameras were used to capture images during the fatigue experiments.

Figure 1. Peel stopper shape and material alignment

2.1. Fatigue Test procedure

The STT specimens were loaded under two different fatigue loads. Table 1 summarizes the load magnitudes as well as the load ratio and frequency of the fatigue tests. The first fatigue load was used to propagate the crack up to the peel stopper tip, and the second fatigue load was imposed to drive the crack in the PU/foam interface, up to the arrest point. The tests were ended when a new crack appeared on the opposite side of the peel stopper and started propagating.

Fatigue test data		First fatigue load	Second fatigue load
Fatigue load [N]	maximum	380	950
Fatigue load [N]	minimum	76	190
Load Ratio		0.2	0.2
Frequency		2 Hz	2 Hz

Table 1. Fatigue test load conditions

Figure 2. STT specimen dimensions and set-up.

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

The finite element model was developed in the commercial FE package ANSYS 15.0 [18]. The model is used to identify the specimen crack loading conditions such as the energy release rate and mode mixity angle as the crack length increases. By using a re-meshing algorithm, the crack loading conditions are used to simulate fatigue crack growth in the facesheet/foam and PU/foam interface. Since the crack in all cases propagated up to the peel stopper tip and then got deflected, the debonded area in the FE simulations would follow the path of the peel stopper angle. The Finite element model represents the STT set-up without including the parts that remain unloaded below the debonded facesheet, Figure 3. The peel stopper shape is meshed in the core structure sharing nodes with the foam core elements. After crack propagation in the PU/foam interface has occurred the re-meshing allows for the nodes to be separated. In figure 3 the crack tip elements are shown at the different positions.

Figure 3. STT finite element model representation. Crack propagating at facesheet/foam interface Crack propagating at the PU/foam interface Crack at the arrest point. Top: overall model with FE meshing. Bottom: Zoom of mesh around crack tip.

The mesh is created by using 8-node plane strain elements (PLANE 183) with a global element size of 1mm. The crack tip is meshed at the respective bi-material interface with an element size of 10 μm . The facesheet and foam materials were modelled as being transversely orthotropic while the PU/glass fibers material of the peel stopper was modelled as isotropic, Table 2.

Materials	In-plane Young's modulus (E_x)	Through thickness Young's modulus (E_y)	Shear modulus (G_{xy})	Poisson's ratio (ν_{xy})	Source
DIVINYCELL H100	56 MPa	128 MPa	32 MPa	0.2	Measured
E-glass/epoxy	18.6 Gpa	--	2.7 GPa	0.4	Measured
PU	100 MPa	100 MPa	--	--	Measured
PU/glass fibers	--	--	--	--	--

Table 2. Material properties

4. FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION / EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS COMPARISON

As shown in Figure 3, the crack propagation and fatigue experiment is modelled in three separate stages:

- Propagation in the facesheet/foam interface
- Propagation in the PU/foam interface
- Crack arrest

Energy release rate / Mode mixity angle

Figure 4 show the evolution of energy release rate and mode mixity angle with respect to crack length. It is observed that the energy release rate always decreases until the arrest point is met. An abrupt change signifies that the second fatigue load amplitude was imposed. The mode mixity of the crack tip also changes considerably as the crack length increases. The shear component (mode II) initially is very low but increases fast. Especially at stage b the mode mixity decreases very rapidly since the crack is propagating at a 10^0 angle towards the inner part of the core structure. The increase in negative mode II component at the arrest point shows a high tendency of the crack to return to the upper interface. Under such loading conditions the increased fracture toughness of the peel stopper,

achieved by the inclusion of fibers in the PU material, is essential for its performance. Since no cracks occur in the PU peel stopper, the initiation of a new crack is required. Due to this stage c of the experiment take place over a considerably longer period, as will be elaborated in the next section.

Figure 4. Energy release rate and mode mixity relation to crack length and load amplitude

5. RESULTS

5.1. Comparison of FE and DIC

The FE simulation of the STT specimen with the crack located at the arrest point, stage c, has been used to capture the major strains at the core material behind the peel stopper. Figure 5, shows the major principal strain field as observed from the DIC images captured during the fatigue tests and the respective field calculated from the FE model.

A comparison shows that the strain concentration in the foam can be captured by the FE model. The model predicts strain values close to the average of the ones observed from DIC. In all cases the observed high strains are an outcome of the local bending of the peel stopper and not the result of stress concentration at the crack. To predict the arrest time, or the number of cycles during stage c) of the experiment, it is necessary to devise a way to relate the highest strain values to the re-initiation process of cracks. Since crack re-initiation algorithms have not been developed and specific material tests conducted, the prediction of the remaining fatigue life is made by using fatigue data for H100 foams from literature.

Figure 5. DIC-FEM major principal strain field comparison. The four pictures above demonstrate the crack path in each of the four specimens. The up-left specimen only showed a difference in the crack path that can be explained by the mode I dominant loading at small crack lengths, fig.4. All specimens though show the same strain distribution at the arrest point which correlates well with the FE predictions

5.2. Maximum strain

The calculation of the major principal strain field, as depicted in Figure 5, was made for several crack lengths from the peel stopper tip and up to the arrest point. The maximum value of strain was recorded for the case of the maximum and minimum fatigue load value, Table 1. In Figure 6 the maximum and minimum major principal strains, ϵ_{max} and ϵ_{min} at the crack initiation point in the core for the max and min fatigue load value are plotted together against their respective loading cycle. In Figure 6b, the respective strain ratio $R_\epsilon = \epsilon_{min}/\epsilon_{max}$ is shown as the crack propagates in the PU/core interface.

Figure 6. Major principal strain

It can be seen that as the crack approaches the arrest point, the strains at the re-initiation point behind the peel stopper increase. Since at stage (c), the crack is not propagating any more, the strain values remain constant for the remaining arrest time, until a new crack initiates behind the peel stopper. As discussed previously, the crack re-initiating behind the peel stopper can be attributed to the major principal strain values. To assess this, the strain ratio at the initiation point can give a clear indication the process of re-initiation. It is seen that the ratio is not constant as the crack expands in the peel stopper. The ratio reaches its maximum value at the arrest point where it is equal to $R_e=0.39$. It should be noted that the applied load ratio in experiments and also the model is constant at $R_L=0.2$.

5.3. Arrest time prediction

To predict the total time of arrest based on the calculated strains, shear strain fatigue data are considered from the work of Burman [19] and DIAB [20]. The data correspond to shear strain fatigue tests of H100 DIVINYCELL conducted on sandwich beams in four-point bending. The stress or equivalently the strain ratio during the fatigue tests was defined at $R_s=0.1$. To account for the effect of strain ratio on the fatigue damage accumulation in the foam and to effectively compare the FE calculated strains to the DIABS H100 fatigue data, the maximum to minimum strain difference is calculated,

$$\Delta\varepsilon = (1 - R) * \varepsilon_{max} \quad (1)$$

Where, ε represents the shear strain from the fatigue data as well as the major principal strains from the DIC measurements and FE calculations. Figure 7 shows the observed strains and respective arrest time in comparison to the provided H100 fatigue data. The average fatigue data curve is used to predict how many cycles can be expected before crack arrest occurs for the STT specimens.

Figure 7. Strain-number of cycles fatigue data comparison

From Figure 7 it is seen that the FE model predicts that the average STT specimen can withstand a total of more than 200.000 cycles. That corresponds to almost three times the number of cycles corresponding to the crack having reached arrest point. Thus, the presence of the peel stopper in the conducted tests have almost tripled the fatigue life of the specimens in comparison with foam cored STT sandwich beams without embedded peel stoppers..

6. CONCLUSIONS

A numerical simulation tool was developed to simulate and predict the fatigue response and expected life time of sandwich beams with embedded crack stoppers. Part of the calculations included fatigue crack propagation simulation in two bi-material interfaces, crack kinking simulation as well as strain field extraction for crack initiation prediction. The STT set-up specimen and DIC data have been used to validate the FE models predictions. The specimens life was separated in three stages from crack propagation in the facesheet/foam interface, the propagation in the peel stopper/foam interface, and finally crack arrest. It was shown that it is possible to predict the effective life time of sandwich beams.

Importantly, the post arrest behavior can be predicted and the potential for improving the peel stopper design depending on the loading conditions has been indicated. However, it appears that the model in combination with the H100 fatigue data from literature overestimate the potential of the peel stopper as none of the tests lasted that many cycles. This could be explained by the difference in stress ratio R for the foam fatigue data from literature and in the current tests. The effect of R on fatigue life might not be entirely captured by the $\Delta\varepsilon$ conversion of the strains. However, the data shows that the ability of the peel stopper to arrest propagating cracks is sensitive to the developing strain values. It is thus clear that a small adjustment in the resulting strain levels could lead to a significant increase of the expected lifetime.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Zenkert "An introduction to sandwich construction" London: Chameleon Press Ltd, 1995
- [2] Erdogan, F., 'Bonded dissimilar materials containing cracks parallel to the interface', *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 231-240 (1971).
- [3] Dundurs, J. Edge-bonded dissimilar orthogonal elastic wedges. *J.Appl.Mech.* 36. 650-652.(1969)
- [4] Hutchinson J.W., Suo Z., "Mixed Mode Cracking in Layered Materials", *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 29, pp. 63-191. 1992
- [5] He_Hutchinson_Kinking of a crack out of an interface. *J.Appl.Mech.* 56. 270-278.(1989)
- [6] Suo, Z.. Singularities, interfaces and cracks in dissimilar media. *Proc. R. Sot. Land.* A427,331-358. (1990)
- [7] Wang, T. C., Mar. 1994. Kinking of an interface crack between two dissimilar anisotropic elastic solids. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 31 (5), 629–641.
- [8] Krueger, R. "Virtual Crack Closure Technique: History, Approach and Applications," *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, Vol. 57, No. 2, 2004, pp. 109-143.
- [9] Berggreen C. Damage tolerance in debonded sandwich structures. PhD. Thesis. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark; 2004.
- [10] Berggreen, C., Simonsen, B. C., Borum, K. K., Feb. 2007. Experimental and numerical study of interface crack propagation in foam-cored sandwich beams. *Journal of Composite Materials* 41 (4), 493–520.
- [11] Bak, B.L.V., Turon, A., Lindgaard, E., Lund, E., 2014. A Simulation Method for High-Cycle Fatigue-Driven Delamination using a Cohesive Zone Model, - under review
- [12] Hirose Y, Matsubara G, Hojo M, Matsuda H, Inamura F. Evaluation of modified crack arrester by fracture toughness tests under mode I type and mode II type loading for foam core sandwich panel. In: *Proc. US-Japan conference on composite materials 2008*, Tokyo, Japan, 2008.
- [13] Hirose, Y., Matsuda, H., Matsubara, G., Hojo, M., Inamura, F., Aug. 2012. Proposal of the concept of splice-type arrester for foam core sandwich panels. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 43 (8), 1318–1325.
- [14] Jakobsen J, Bozhevolnaya E, Thomsen OT. New peel stopper concept for sandwich structures. *Compos Sci Technol* 2007;67:3378–85.
- [15] Jakobsen J, Andreassen JH, Bozhevolnaya E. Crack kinking of a delamination at an inclined core junction interface in a sandwich beam. *Eng Fract Mech*2008;75(16):4759–73.
- [16] Bozhevolnaya E, Jakobsen J, Thomsen OT. Performance of sandwich panels with peel stoppers, strain. *Int J Exp Mech* 2009;45:349–57.
- [17] Moslemian, R., Karlsson, A. M., Berggreen, C., Dec. 2011. Accelerated fatigue crack growth simulation in a bimaterial interface. *International Journal of Fatigue* 33 (12), 1526–1532.
- [18] ANSYS® Academic Research, Release 15.0
- [19] Burman, M., Magnusson, B., Fatigue testing of H60, H100 and H200. Technical report (DIAB), KTH (Sweden). 2008
- [20] DIAB. Divinycell H-Grade Technical data, 2014. Laholm (Sweden) (<http://www.diabgroup.com>).